

Article: „Accuracy, Clinical Utility, and Usability of a Wireless Self-Guided Fetal Heart Rate Monitor”

Summary:

The article “Accuracy, Clinical Utility, and Usability of a Wireless Self-Guided Fetal Heart Rate Monitor” describes a study aimed at evaluating the accuracy, clinical usefulness, and practical use of a new wireless, self-guided monitor of fetal and maternal heart rate. The device was designed to enable pregnant women to independently perform short fetal heart rate recordings both in clinical settings and at home, as part of a maternity care model partially based on telemedicine.

The authors analyze whether such a monitor can be reliable compared with a standard cardiotocograph, whether it provides traces sufficient for clinical assessment, and whether it is intuitive and easy to use for individuals without specialized training.

Between July and September 2020, a total of 81 women participated in the study, preparing 126 recordings. The gestational age ranged from 12 to 40 weeks. The analysis compared the accuracy of the fetal heart rate (FHR) monitor with cardiotocography.

Table 1 presents detailed demographic and clinical characteristics of the participants, including age, BMI, gestational age, number of pregnancies and births, as well as anatomical factors such as placental location. The diversity of these parameters indicates that the device was tested in a population that accurately reflects the real variability of pregnant patients, which increases the practical relevance of the results.

The fetal heart rate monitor was operated both by medical staff and by the patients themselves. In both groups, the median time to detect FHR was 0.5 minutes, and in most cases it took less than 2 minutes. The women participating in the study did not experience difficulties using the device independently at home.

The main aim of the study was to compare the accuracy of the wireless monitor with that of a standard cardiotocograph. The Bland–Altman plot (Figure 4) illustrates the key data from this analysis.

The results showed only a small difference between the average fetal heart rate values measured by the new device and those obtained using traditional CTG. From a clinical standpoint, the new device provided results equivalent to standard equipment used for assessing basic fetal heart rate parameters. This is an important finding, as the reliability of measurements directly influences prenatal care decisions, and any discrepancies from the true heart rate could lead to incorrect clinical conclusions.

Table 2 assessed the time required to detect FHR from the beginning of the recording. The median for all participants was 0.5 minutes, indicating that both healthcare professionals and pregnant women were able to locate FHR quickly.

The analysis also included recordings with ≥ 1 minute of continuous FHR. It was found that 95% of recordings performed by medical staff met this criterion. A large proportion of home recordings showed similar performance to those made in the clinical environment. After submitting the recordings, only minor time differences were noted between FHR measurement

durations recorded by medical staff and those recorded at home by pregnant participants. The study also considered signal quality indicators, such as the presence of accelerations and signal stability without interruptions.

In the study summarized in Table 3, pregnant participants evaluated the usability and ease of operating the device. The analysis was based solely on the participants' subjective impressions. The table includes aspects such as device functionality, intuitiveness, simplicity of use, and comfort when used both in the clinic and at home.

The System Usability Scale (SUS), one of the most reliable tools for assessing usability, was applied. The results are expressed as percentiles. The SUS scores presented in the table show that both in clinical and home settings, the device ranked in the 96th–100th percentile. This indicates that the FHR monitor performed exceptionally well compared with similar devices.

Another scale used in the study was the Adjectival Rating Scale. Similar to the SUS, it involves selecting a usability rating from 1 to 7. In this study, the median score was 6, indicating that most of the participating women were satisfied with the usability of the device.

Summarizing the conducted study, it becomes clear that the fetal heart rate monitor is a highly accurate device. The analyses and the Bland–Altman plot demonstrated that this monitor does not differ from the standard CTG in terms of fetal heart rate measurement. Moreover, it produces high-quality recordings that can be interpreted both by healthcare professionals and pregnant women. The results are reliable and easy to read.

Pregnant women evaluated the heart rate monitor as exceptionally easy to use, which is supported by the high SUS score. They have no difficulties operating the device and are eager to use it.

Healthcare professionals assess the home FHR recordings as clinically useful, complete, and intact, which allows for an improved level of prenatal care even in a home environment.

Autors:

Paul Porter- He is an Associate Professor, Director, and founder of Freeman Road Pty Ltd. He has 34 publications to his credits. Additionally, he is a medical researcher and a pediatrician. His research focuses particularly on the respiratory system, prenatal care, and mental health disorders in children. He also serves as the Chair of the Research and Ethics Committee at Ramsay Health Care in Western and South Australia. Article popular „Accuracy, Clinical Utility, and Usability of a Wireless Self-Guided Fetal Heart Rate Monitor”, „Accuracy, interpretability and usability study of a wireless self-guided fetal heartbeat monitor compared to cardiotocography”.

Fleur Muirhead- She is a doctor at Queensland Health and a scientific researcher. Her particular interests are focused on obstetrics and gynecology, and she is currently developing her expertise in this area. She is a volunteer and conducts independent scientific research. She holds advanced qualifications in obstetrics and is a co-author of the preprint of a study on a fetal heart rate monitor. Article “Accuracy, Clinical Utility, and Usability of a Wireless Self-Guided Fetal Heart Rate Monitor”. She has 3 publications.

Joanna Brisbane- He is the Research and Clinical Trials Manager at Joondalup Health Campus. His research focuses primarily on pediatric cases, with a particular emphasis on the respiratory system. Article “A smartphone-based algorithm comprising cough analysis and patient-reported symptoms identifies acute exacerbations of asthma: a prospective, double blind, diagnostic accuracy study”.

Brooke Schneider- Research psychologist, Clinical Neuropsychology Working Group, Department of Psychiatry and Psychotherapy, University Medical Center Hamburg-Eppendorf, Germany. She has 4 publications.

Jennifer Choveaux- Researcher, her work focuses primarily on prenatal diagnostics, pregnant women, fetal heart rate monitoring, and all related monitoring devices.

Natasha Bear- She is a biostatistician with a clinical background and 15 years of experience as a physiotherapist specializing in childhood disability and pediatric rehabilitation. She has authored over 50 publications and is the owner of a statistics company that provides data analysis for medical and clinical research projects. She collaborates with the ORIGINS project.

Jenne Carson- Doctor of Physiology, School of Population and Public Health, author of 11 publications. She also completed studies in Geophysics and Petroleum Engineering.

Kym Jones- She is a specialist in obstetrics and gynecology, holds a diploma in diagnostic ultrasound in obstetrics and gynecology, and provides clinical care for pregnant women. She has 4 publications to her credits. She is also a sonologist. Her interests include first-trimester fetal assessment, high-risk pregnancies with threatened miscarriage, pregnancies after cesarean section, pelvic floor ultrasonography, and post-miscarriage care.

Dessire Silva- Professor Desiree Silva is the Co-Director of ORIGINS and a Professor of Pediatrics at the University of Western Australia and Joondalup Health Campus. She obtained her medical qualifications in the United Kingdom and completed specialist pediatric training in Western Australia and the Northern Territory. Her interests focus on neurodevelopmental

disorders, and she has over 20 years of experience caring for children diagnosed with ADHD, autism, anxiety, and developmental disorders. She has published in international journals, including *Pediatrics* and *Lancet Psychiatry*.

Cliff Neppe- He is a specialist in obstetrics and gynecology with the FRANZCOG qualification, serving as the Director of Obstetrics and Gynecology at Joondalup Health Campus. He provides care for patients with both low- and high-risk pregnancies and is interested in the development of telemedicine, particularly in home fetal heart rate monitoring.

The journal ACOG Obstetrics and Gynecology focuses on promoting clinical practice in the field of obstetrics and gynecology, as well as other related medical disciplines. It is aimed primarily at gynecologists and obstetricians, publishing articles mainly on pregnancy, perinatal care, gynecological specialties, infertility-related endocrinology, and urogynecology. The journal features publications such as:

- Original research articles (clinical, translational)
- Systematic reviews / meta-analyses / analyses
- Other types of manuscripts: editorial comments, articles discussing clinical practice or guidelines, clinical reports, case analyses
- In practice: works related to pregnancy, childbirth, gynecology, procedures, complications, and women's health.

According to metrics, the Impact Factor for 2024 is 4.7. The average number of citations over two years is approximately 3.22, and the h-index is 268. The journal has been published since 1953. Every June, the publishers release a range of indicators based on article citations.

For the journal Obstetrics & Gynecology, the 2019 Impact Factor was 5.524, which ranked it 6th out of 82 journals in the field of obstetrics and gynecology. The five-year Impact Factor (5-year IF) reflects the average number of citations of articles published in the past five years. In 2019, it was 5.618.

The Immediacy Index indicates the average number of citations received in the same year an article is published. For Obstetrics & Gynecology, in 2019, it was 1.316. The Eigenfactor assesses the journal's influence by considering both the number of citations and the significance of their sources, while excluding self-citations. In 2019, the journal's Eigenfactor was 0.04793.

